

Supporting Participatory &
Inclusive Practices in WGI of the IPCC:

SUMMARY REPORT OF ACTIVITIES & IMPACTS

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by Shift Collaborative

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better world

Background & Introduction

The Working Group I (WGI) contribution to the IPCC's Sixth Assessment Report (AR6) ran for about 4 years from 2018 through 2021. Within the IPCC procedures, it states that when selecting participants for report scoping meetings and report authors, efforts should be made to strive for regional and gender balance, but there are no further guidelines for insuring participatory and inclusive practices throughout the report drafting process. From the outset of AR6, WGI had identified that diversifying the participation of authors in the WG was a priority. Efforts included setting a welcoming and supportive environment for new authors, introducing a Code of Conduct at the first lead author meeting (LAM 1, 2018), running post-LAM surveys with authors that included a range of questions about participation and inclusion, and working with [SHIFT Collaborative](#) beginning at LAM 2 to provide additional support for creating an inclusive and participatory culture. Together with the Bureau and Technical Support Unit (TSU), SHIFT designed resources and facilitated a series of activities for authors in the time surrounding LAMs 2, 3 and 4.

This report, written by SHIFT Collaborative with input from the WGI TSU, recaps the activities undertaken, and summarises the author feedback that was gathered after each LAM. It is a “looking back” on the past activities and survey data to see the extent to which we can identify what has changed and what works to create an inclusive, participatory culture in this kind of global, scientific setting. The report will identify themes for a second phase of information gathering and analysis (planned between April and July 2022) that will inform a deeper understanding of impacts and strategies to strengthen diversity and collaboration.

Methods

This report is based on the review of LAM author surveys (7 in total) conducted by the TSU and SHIFT, and the related activities and resources that were delivered to authors during the drafting of the WGI AR6 report. Surveys were sent to authors at specific times during the report drafting process, usually after a LAM, or for CLA's, after training sessions the survey aimed to capture a debrief of the recent meeting and to help prepare for the next stage of the process. Questions were usually orientated around gathering information on the scientific content, logistical, and inclusive and participatory aspects of the meeting. Appendix A contains information on the WGI surveys and data sources.

Limitations:

The survey data has some limitations:

- Generally, participation in the surveys was over 50% of all authors with some exceptions, for example, when only the CLAs were surveyed. As such, we can see a diversity of experiences and opinions in the survey comments, however, we do not know how the activities affected authors that did not complete a survey or why they did not.
- Authors were asked to report about their demographic status “if they were willing”, so this data is not comprehensive. In LAM 1 and 2 surveys 6% and 1% respectively opted not to share their gender and in the LAM 3 survey this increased to 12% of respondents. The question was not asked in the final LAM 4 survey. We do know that among those who did share this information, the female survey responses are within the range of overall participation in the WG (between 25 – 31%), and the responses across countries likewise is representative of author participation. This suggests that generally the survey responses represent the diversity of authors, however, using cross tabs by gender may not be reliable.

- The survey also asked a series of questions about barriers authors were experiencing that do provide some cross analysis. These barriers

included, for example, “being female” or “being a new author” as well as things like “lack of time”. However, respondents were able to select “this is not a problem for me” which does not tell us if the person IS a woman, but does not associate barriers with that, or if they are not a woman.

The approach to this report is aligned with developmental evaluation, or “live time” evaluation designed to support learning and adaptive action. In developmental evaluation we often use a pattern of analysis referred to as what, so what, now what?

- **WHAT did we do?**
- **SO.... WHAT happened?**
What were the results or impacts on people or places?
What did we learn? What questions do we have?
- **NOW WHAT?**
What are the next steps we need to take to adapt, improve or strengthen impacts?

The following sections unpack the results of this developmental evaluation.

WHAT WE DID: *Activities & Resources*

This section summarizes the activities and resources that were delivered by SHIFT, the TSU and the WGI Bureau between LAM 2 (held in person), January 2019, and leading up to LAM 4, Pre-LAM 4 (held virtually), June-September 2020. There is also some LAM 1 data included as relevant background. The activities were designed to support authors' awareness, skills and tools to **co-create an inclusive culture within the WG.**

The framing invitation for authors to engage in this journey was:

How might we co-create a space that is inclusive and collaborative, and that utilizes our diverse cultures, knowledge and experience for outcomes of the highest quality and impact?

- What does an **inclusive, collaborative culture** look like?
- What **tools and approaches** are useful in supporting an inclusive, collaborative culture going forward?
- **How can I personally contribute** to strengthening participation, collaboration and inclusion? What is my role or “learning edge”?

Overview of Activities & Resources

(see chart next page):

From the outset, the approach was to engage all authors as voluntary learners and leaders in supporting this culture. At the same time, it was identified that CLAs had the potential to be key influencers within their chapter groups and specific facilitation training was offered to this group. Tailored coaching was also offered to chapter groups at LAM 3 and continued with several groups between LAM 3 and 4.

WG I INCLUSIVE PRACTICE ACTIVITIES & RESOURCES

CLA Facilitation Training & Resources

A 2-hour CLA training was offered the day before the start of each LAM and typically had close to 100% participation. The training started with **core Facilitation Skills and Tools** at LAM 2, then **Resources for Consensus Building** at LAM 3 and **Facilitating Virtual Meetings** prior to Pre-LAM 4. SHIFT was available to CLAs for 1-to-1 discussion or troubleshooting during all LAMs. There are 5 CLA Toolkits available on the shared drive (see Appendix B).

Engaging All Authors as Inclusive Learners & Leaders

Plenary Activities

With SHIFT Collaborative being included into the WGI environment in LAM2, the work to strengthen inclusive culture was introduced in the opening plenary of this meeting. During the week, all authors were invited to participate in open poster boards to define the type of culture they wanted to create and share the barriers to achieving that. These inputs were shared back to authors in a closing plenary and are shared below. The closing plenary also included an anonymous poll to hear back generally from authors about their experience with inclusion and participation through the week.

Mindsets

we are aware of the differences
we can stand in the shoes of another
we are open minded, flexible, adaptive
we value everyone as a thinker
we acknowledge the power imbalance around roles and privilege

Practices

- encourage everyone to speak
- raise hands, use rounds, share the air time
- speak slowly and clearly
- Leaders model inclusive practices
- create common ground rules
- take time for 1to1 discussions

Structures

- everyone has access to training and resources for group collaboration
- scheduled time for social connections
- rules for teleconferences such as speaking slowly, succinctly, documenting
- use google docs, slack and other tech tools

Open and Targeted Mini-Dialogue Sessions and Resources

Several open “mini- dialogue” sessions were offered in each LAM and attended by an average of 40 different authors over the period of the week. These 1-hour sessions were designed to offer a space for authors to engage with each other around topics such as cultural awareness, unconscious bias and power.

They also offered some light education and practical resources around each topic. Topics were selected in response to input from authors in surveys. There were 8 different resources produced for these sessions that are available on the shared drive (see Appendix B).

In LAM 3, as the culture within the WG began to reflect a shared language of inclusion and some core practices within Chapters were adopted, there was an effort to broaden facilitation skills beyond the CLAs. The thinking was that if all authors were participant/facilitators in their Chapters this could take the pressure off the CLA to be holding all the new practices and also support culture shifts. For example, the consensus decision making process, hand signals and tip sheet were introduced to all authors in the LAM 3 opening plenary session rather than putting pressure on busy CLAs to orient their chapters. In Pre-LAM 4 open author sessions, the use of group agreements (and a related Resource Guide) was introduced as a specific tool that CLAs had identified as being useful. This work to engage all authors as co-facilitators in some fashion was just beginning.

Dedicated sessions were offered to Bureau and TSU in advance of LAM 3, and during the LAM (incoming) Review Editors were also oriented to the new practices including consensus decision making. Although attendance was small for these sessions, the TSU and Bureau were advising on, vetting and supporting all of the SHIFT activities in advance of, and debriefing them following each LAM. Various Bureau members attended mini-dialogue sessions and/or the CLA Training sessions.

Tailored Coaching with Chapters

Several CLAs reached out to SHIFT for support with specific challenges during LAM 3 and two groups had light, dedicated coaching between LAM 3 and 4.

Switching to a Virtual Working Environment

While CLAs were encouraged from the beginning of AR6 to engage their chapter members virtually between LAMs, this approach became imperative with the onset of COVID. The TSU provided guidance documents and supports, researched various platforms and ran a purely virtual LAM 4 (and pre-LAM activities). SHIFT offered several training sessions and resources to support the facilitation of inclusive and participatory environments online. This switch, combined with other pressures from the COVID environment (such as working from home), exacerbated the stress for authors who were learning new ways of working.

No longer being able to meet in person created new challenges (and some opportunities) for creating an inclusive environment. On a very practical level, chapter groups were now straddling multiple time zones to find appropriate times to meet, which introduced a level of fatigue and inconvenience for some authors, depending on where they were located.

In several cases, it also required sub-groups of authors to meet asynchronously rather than as a whole group together. Activities which previously would have been undertaken together in person, now required groups to switch to the use of virtual, digital platforms. Inequities related to internet or digital access became apparent and presented challenges for several Chapter groups.

So ... What?

WHAT were the impacts? What changed?

This section presents the main findings from the author surveys and includes feedback from SHIFT's experiences throughout the process.

Some authors experience multiple barriers to participation.

In the post LAM 1 Survey:

- 38% of respondents (n=90) identified that **being a first-time author** was either a minor or a major barrier to their participation
- 29% identified that **“feeling as though others were more expert than they were”** was a minor or major barrier
- 26% identified **fluency in English** as a minor or major barrier.
- A majority (88%) of those who identified feeling others were more expert were also 1st time authors.
- 61% of those who said feeling others were more expert was a barrier also identified fluency in English as a barrier.
- Although only 26% identified fluency in English as a barrier, just over half of these also named being a first-time author and feeling others were more expert as barriers.
- Other people dominating discussions was the other major barrier that authors identified in LAM 1 (27% of respondents) and just over half of these are also first-time authors.

The portion of authors reporting that being a 1st time author is a barrier for them is fairly steady and the proportion of those authors who ALSO experience one or more other barriers is also relatively steady. This suggests that there is a small but important segment of authors who are experiencing multiple barriers.

BARRIER SURVEY	LAM 1 Survey		LAM 2 Survey		LAM 3 Survey	
	All Authors (N = 90)	As a portion of those for whom being a 1st time author is a barrier (N=34)	All Authors (N = 86)	As a portion of those for whom being a 1st time author is a barrier (N=30)	All Authors (N = 101)	As a portion of those for whom being a 1st time author is a barrier (N=31)
Being a first-time author is a barrier	(34) 38%		(30) 35%		(31) 31%	
Feel others are more expert	(26) 29%	(23) 68%	(34) 40%	(21) 70%	(40) 40%	(22) 71%
Feel others dominate	(24) 27%	(14) 41%	(32) 37%	(15) 50%	(40) 40%	(17) 55%
English fluency is a barrier	(23) 26%	(14) 41%	(26) 30%	(10) 33%	(34) 34%	(13) 42%
Differences in cultural communication/norms is a barrier			(36) 42%		(45) 45%	

Authors reported increased barriers to participation over time.

In addition to the barriers identified in the graph above, lack of time was the most common barrier that authors reported at 67% for LAM 2 and 70% for LAM 3. **Lack of time** was added as a new option in the LAM 2 survey because so many authors commented on this as a barrier for them in LAM 1.

The second most frequent barrier named was **cultural communication and norms** which increased from 42% in LAM 2 to 45% in LAM 3. Those reporting that being a 1st time author was a barrier for them declined slightly while there was an increase in other barriers being reported. **Feeling that others were more expert** and the **experience of others dominating discussions** both increased to 40% from 29% and 27% in LAM 1.

This increase might be an indicator of survey respondents being more aware of inclusive practices than they were in LAM 1 and “calling it out”. It may also reflect that the nature of the work becomes more complex (more cross-chapter issues) and contentious as authors work toward LAM 4. In addition, the switch to virtual environments during COVID may have played a contributing role.

Virtual competency has increased; however, in-person convening is preferred to virtual.

The virtual nature of Pre-LAM 4, in a COVID context where people were working at home, presented additional challenges for author participation including juggling childcare, work and WGI activities, increased time pressures and managing group discussions across time zones, which were the most common challenges authors named. Some authors felt that it also added barriers to non-English speakers reducing those voices even further (in survey comments).

Notwithstanding author's overall preference for working in person (57% reported virtual meetings were either "not at all" or "less inclusive" than in person in the LAM 4 survey), there were some who identified the virtual space increased their participation (for example by being able to watch session recordings or use the chat). There was also appreciation for the guides and lessons about virtual meetings and for CLAs that implemented additional virtual tools and approaches to support inclusion. Examples: Chat box helpful for inclusion, CLAs are paying more attention to chat now.

The experience with virtual meetings and the guidance documents and resources provided by the TSU and SHIFT supported increased skills and comfort with technology that will be useful in a future, post COVID context to support more efficient, inclusive chapter work between in-person meetings.

Authors with concerns about inclusion and participation in their chapter groups often attribute the situation to a lack of CLA/facilitation skills.

The surveys allowed for authors to provide written comments if desired on their barriers to participation. The list below identifies some feedback on the importance of inclusive facilitation within chapter meetings (LAM 3 Survey Summary).

- *I know of 3 chapters that are struggling where CLAs still dominate.*
- *It is still common for a few to dominate discussions. Our CLA needs help to better engage those from other cultures.*
- *We need outside facilitators, or coaches to observe (for an hour) and assess our chapter functioning.*
- *Between a lot of new authors from different backgrounds and a poor chair our chapter meetings are a waste of time.*

CLA facilitation training is an effective way to increase inclusive group practices. CLAs have new, demonstrated facilitation skills and tools to support inclusion.

Authors often look to the CLAs to support the inclusive culture of Chapter groups:

“CLAs need to pay attention to their chapter dynamics and ensure integration of the whole chapter team.”

And when groups are not functioning effectively, many authors see more skilled facilitation as the answer:

“Keep reminding CLAs that they may have many people new to IPCC in their chapter and that they should make a strong effort to try to engage all LAs in discussions. Objective facilitation would help.”

(LAM 1 comments)

The focus of the CLA training at LAM 2 was Core Facilitation Skills & Tools which included topics such as group dynamics, ice breakers, relationship building, facilitation tools and approaches for group discussion. A post survey of CLAs indicated that **82% of respondents** had used new tools or approaches during LAM 2. At the LAM 3 training CLAs named a number of inclusive tools or approaches they had used either during LAM 2 or between LAM 2 and 3, such as:

- *Socializing together;*
- *Using “rounds” to gather input from all, Paraphrasing, Summarizing, inviting people to comment, holding back my own comments, use of the “bicycle rack” (a space where outstanding issues are parked for attention later)*
- *Being more perceptive of others body language/expressions, changing seating;*
- *Encourage post meeting feedback via email;*
- *Entire chapter takes responsibility for each section, rotating the chair/facilitator;*
- *Small groups to bring ideas/proposals back to whole group (used online as well),*
- *Adding video to online meetings;*
- *Using SharePoint for all documents (a platform useable from all countries)*
- *Holding online meetings twice in the day to allow for different time zones.*

Several CLAs reported using multiple new tools and approaches: Change of perspective, check-ins, break out groups, individual speaking time, group agreement around norms, awareness of the stages of group development.

Coming into training in advance of LAM 3, many CLAs identified that their biggest challenge was participation of all authors including engaging authors in discussion and in doing the work. After the LAM 3 CLA training on Consensus, a majority of CLAs identified that the consensus tip sheet, hand signals and a number of other approaches or tools were useful:

- *very helpful session*
- *useful examples and materials*
- *liked learning what other CLAs are doing/sharing ideas*

The LAM 3 survey showed that 87% of authors rated chapter inclusion and participation as either good or excellent, supporting the positive feedback from CLA's regarding their use of new approaches. The extent to which the CLA training is influencing this, and other factors that may be at play, is not totally clear, however, it appears that the CLA training is one contributing factor.

“In my chapter we do not have inclusion problems, and the 2 CLAs always make sure everybody participates to the discussions. However, not all chapters work this well, so it is good to keep on the participatory training.”

Tailored coaching can be useful to problem solve specific challenges within chapter groups.

Chapter coaching was offered on a voluntary basis from LAM 2, however, it took some time for CLAs to get to know SHIFT Collaborative and build some trust in the process. Several reached out for conversations during LAM 3 and two others had some light coaching between LAM 3 and Pre-LAM 4. There has not yet been follow-up to understand if or how this coaching affected chapter functioning.

There is also no formal assessment of chapter inclusive practices. While some CLAs have implemented feedback polls for their members, this is an internal practice and not shared with the TSU. Likewise, author surveys that ask them to rate participation in their chapter group are anonymous, so there is not a clear sense of how each chapter group is doing, or which groups might need additional support.

Some authors have made suggestions that dedicated coaching support and/or external facilitation be available for/during Chapter meetings, and/or that the TSU conduct assessments of chapter inclusive practices.

To date however, the TSU has opted for a voluntary process. It may be useful to explore some kind of “middle ground” approach that preserves choice and makes Chapter supports more accessible.

- *More of the same, plus in-chapter (during chapter meetings) coaching and facilitation would be great.*
- *I am interested in measuring how these interventions are impacting the process.*

Cultural diversity is a strength for the WG, and there is a need to improve cross cultural intelligence.

In the LAM 3 survey, 45% of authors (n=101) name **differences in culture** as an ongoing barrier to their participation. Many, but not all of these also identify **English fluency** as a barrier (34%). This suggests that there is a larger group of authors who see improved cross cultural intelligence as a means to improve participation.

The 1-hour “mini dialogues” were the main place that working across cultures was discussed (other topics included unconscious bias, diversity, difference and power. See Appendix B) and they generally attracted approximately 35-40 authors during each LAM. These participants represented diverse cultures and geographies and were generally already informed and or were experiencing barriers to participation in some fashion. Authors’ verbal feedback on the mini-dialogue sessions was generally positive, indicating appreciation for the opportunity to reflect, share and learn from each other. Authors also voiced appreciation for the practical tips and tools.

Given the number of authors naming cross-cultural communication as a barrier to participation, cultural intelligence resources and training could be a high impact area for strengthening inclusion in WGI in the future.

A majority of authors have identified that the training and resources have strengthened their inclusive skills and knowledge, however, this work competes with the time demands of chapter and cross chapter work.

Plenary presentations and polls were generally short and rapid polling indicated that many authors were paying more attention to their own personal attitudes and practices to support inclusion:

- 82% of those who voted in the LAM 2 closing poll (N=130) thought there had been an **increase in awareness about diversity, difference and power** over the week.
- 62% indicated they had **adjusted their own practices** in some way during the week

At the end of LAM 3, 64% of authors surveyed (n=101) felt that **the inclusion and participatory practices work should be continued:**

- *Excellent sessions and helpful information*
- *I wish the definition of "consensus" - agree/reservations/stand aside/block - had been explained before LAM1.*
- *The consensus building leaflet has been useful and widely adopted in our chapter. This is the kind of concrete actions that we need more of.*
- *Please offer these sessions on their own and not at the same time as our meetings so more can attend.*
- *The cultural awareness session helped me understand the differences between eastern and western communication styles and that has helped me in my chapter.*
- *Yes, yes, yes! We are still a long way from being inclusive and it is easy to lapse back in our behaviour.*

While the majority of respondents were supportive of continuing this work, 28% were not sure if these practices should be continued and 8% indicated they should not. Many of those who were “not sure” indicated in comments that their primary concern was balancing time needed for the work, with the time that inclusive practice coaching requires, however, there may be more to understand from this group of authors who are “not sure”. It could be useful to better understand if they are saying this because their chapter is working well, or because the activities to date have not been useful for improving inclusion in their chapter. In addition, it would be helpful to better understand the demographics of these respondents to analyse the role that gender, career phase, and geography play in people’s perceptions.

- *Yes, but it can't be at the expense of getting the job done.*
- *I think plenty has been done already and this is not the only, or most important, priority for our time right now.*
- *Useless activity.*

The SHIFT resources on the document manager system are accessed at rates similar to other documents – about 25%. While the resources are valuable, going forward there is a question around whether or not authors will access them without some support to apply them to their own situations/practices.

Overall, the efforts to date have contributed to a culture of inclusion and participation within WGI, as well as an increased awareness of what else is needed.

At the end of LAM 2, 82% of authors (n=86) responding to the survey said there had been an **increase in awareness about diversity, difference and power** over the week. 62% said they had **personally adapted their behaviour to support inclusion** and 57% indicated that their **chapter group had made changes to support greater inclusion**.

Of the authors responding to the post LAM 3 survey (n=101), 84% and 87% felt that the level of participation respectively in the WG overall, and their chapter groups, was good or excellent.

Our chapter is working well; ... is engaged; ... has a good atmosphere.

In the post LAM 3 survey, a majority of authors surveyed also agreed with these statements:

- *There is openness about culture and difference*
- *Everyone is valued for their contribution*
- *There is respect for new ideas*
- *Everyone has an opportunity to speak*
- *We take time to get to know each other*
- *We use virtual platforms to connect and share materials*
- *Members have time to read material in advance*

One author pointed out that the shift in culture was a mixed blessing in that as participation increased, the complexity of managing diverse inputs grows:

“We have spent considerable time and effort to be inclusive. This makes the writing aspects of our chapter more complicated, as almost all authors are contributing but the assembly is quite complex.”

In the same survey, authors also identified these elements of inclusive culture as needing more attention:

- More work in pairs and small groups
- Asking questions to understand
- Willingness to balance power and address unconscious bias
- Sharing the airtime
- Speaking slowly

- Evaluating our process
- Use of group agreements and rules of productive virtual meetings
- Use of the resources and tools on the DSM
- Cross-cultural awareness

Summary of Themes

1. Some authors experience multiple barriers to participation, for example being a 1st time author, English fluency and being a woman. While small, the proportion who are reporting these challenges is fairly constant which suggests the inclusive activities may not be fully addressing the barriers experienced by this group of authors.
2. A majority of authors have identified that the training and resources have strengthened their inclusive practices, however, this work competes with the time demands of chapter and cross chapter work.
3. In addition to the high ratings for participation and inclusion, a number of authors continue to identify barriers to participation right up to the final pre-LAM 4 survey. It is clear that not all authors are having a positive, inclusive experience in spite of the progress that has been made.
4. Authors with concerns about the lack of inclusion and participation experience this in chapter groups and often attribute the situation to a lack of CLA inclusive facilitation skills.
5. CLA facilitation training is an effective way to increase inclusive group practices. Many CLAs are using new facilitation skills and tools to support inclusion, and authors have noted the positive impacts of this.
6. Tailored chapter coaching can be useful to problem solve specific challenges with CLAs who reach out for support.
7. Cultural diversity is a strength for the WG, and there is a need to improve cross cultural intelligence as a core component of the inclusive practice training.
8. While virtual competency has increased, in-person meetings are preferred to virtual meetings and may support a more participatory and inclusive environment.
9. Overall, the efforts to date have contributed to a growing culture of inclusion and participation within WGI, as well as an increased awareness of what else is needed.

NOW WHAT? Proposed Next Steps

The following suggestions and recommendations have come from the current survey data and experience. Given that there is a second phase of research pending that will build on these findings, it may be premature to act on these, however, it was important to capture the current learnings to date.

Following on this first phase of research, Phase II will gather additional input to address gaps in our understanding of authors experiences, as well as the impacts on their individual practices and the collective inclusive culture of WG1. Specifically, we want to explore the implications of the inclusive practices experience within WG I for authors, their institutions, and future international scientific collaborations. This second phase of research will be concluded by June 30th, 2022.

Author Suggestions to Improve Inclusive Practice

At the end of LAM 3, authors were invited to make suggestions for improving inclusive and participatory practices. The resulting suggestions included:

- Mandatory training for CLAs and all authors between in-person meetings to save time when we are working together; offer webinars between LAMs
- Learn more about one another's cultures to understand one another better and communicate/work together better
- Keep tools practical: e.g., the consensus tip sheet has been well used
- Sharing what works between chapters
- Reminders for all authors at the start of each session can help set the tone (if short!)
- Offer objective facilitator to work with CLA on planning, to be available for troubleshooting and to visit chapter to support assessing situation and ideas
- Continue chapter meals and social times
- Polls or surveys to get feedback - to evaluate how chapters are doing.

SHIFT Recommendations

1. The TSU could consider polling by chapter to gather feedback on inclusive practices. Results should be shared with CLAs and used to assess measurable impacts and changes. The chapter polls could also be the basis for reaching out to specific CLAs to explore if or how they can be supported in their inclusive facilitation practices. Engagement could still be voluntary.
2. Cultural awareness training can be integrated into the CLA Training from the outset and tools made available to all authors (similar to how the consensus tools were introduced in AR6).
3. It would be ideal if CLA training is offered prior to LAM 1 and continues as a “Community of Practice” with additional supports throughout each LAM.
4. Consider modifying survey questions to ensure answers to demographic data and barrier questions can be used as cross tabs for other responses. Ensure each survey has a core set that remains consistent.

Questions that have Emerged (to Inform Phase II Research)

The following questions have emerged from the Phase I research and will inform the Phase II focus and scope.

1. Role of CLAs:

The role of the CLA is clearly important as a contribution to the culture shift.

- a. What are the concerns and objections of those who have not adopted inclusive facilitation practices?
- b. How would CLAs describe the benefits (of the training) for them personally? Have they experienced any changes in attitudes or practices?
- c. What benefits do CLAs identify in their chapters as a result of this work? What changes are they seeing? What is the relationship (if any) between inclusive practices and the ability of the chapter to get work done; to produce high quality work?
- d. What are the most important or impactful practices or tools they have used with their chapter groups?
- e. What are the other factors that have been important contributors to inclusive culture in their chapter group (besides the training or their own skills)?

- f. How would CLAs improve the training for next time? What would they look for in new CLAs being recruited into this work?
- g. See also the questions below for all authors

2. New Authors

- a. Among new authors who experienced more than one barrier (being a 1st year author, plus others such as English, culture, gender) what was helpful for them?
- b. What suggestions would they have for: new authors, for the TSU/Bureau, for a new CLA to strengthen inclusive culture?

3. All Authors

- a. Among all authors experience, what is same/different between the inclusive culture being developed in WGI and their institutional experience?
 - b. How, if at all, has their experience in WGI transferred to their institution or professional practice?
 - c. Given the practical nature of the SHIFT resources, how can they be made more accessible and used more by all authors? Is there some form of knowledge dissemination or virtual dialogue sessions that could happen between LAMs? Are resources curated appropriately to support access? (for CLAs and all authors)
 - d. Are there any additional structures (rules/policies, training, systems or resources) that would strengthen inclusive practice and culture?
 - e. What are the pros and cons of mandatory inclusive practice tools in chapter groups? (For example, if group agreements were required in every chapter?) What are the minimum inclusive practices that all chapters should be accountable for? How can the TSU maintain a voluntary approach to this work and also measure progress and hold groups accountable?
4. How, if at all, is the inclusive and participatory culture affecting the final AR6 report?

Proposed Methods for Phase II Research

1. Interview TSU staff in a small group
2. Survey all CLAs
 - a. Based on responses, host a focus group to explore particular questions/answers in more detail
 - b. Consider if a case study of a successful CLA could be useful for the future (profiling inclusive mindsets, practices and structures/tools that contributed to participatory culture)
 - c. Conduct at least one interview with a CLA that is less supportive of inclusive practice work
3. Host a focus group for up to 12 first-time authors who also represent demographics that typically experience at least one additional barrier.
4. Host a focus group for up to 12 “other” LAs.

APPENDIX A:

WGI SURVEYS / DATA SOURCES

WG1 AR6 LAM 1 Feedback Survey

CLA Training Feedback LAM 2

WG1 AR6 LAM 2 Feedback Survey Summary

CLA Survey Report post LAM 2

SHIFT Notes for TSU on LAM 2

CLA Check In and Feedback Form Summaries from LAM 3

Summary LAM 3 Survey Responses

LAM 3 Survey Responses

Summary LAM 2 and LAM 3 SHIFT Responses

SHIFT Reflections on LAM 3

Survey Pre-LAM 4 Responses September

Summary of Survey Responses Pre-LAM 4

APPENDIX B:

Resources to Support Inclusive and Participatory Culture

LAM1

- Code of Conduct (Bureau/TSU)
- Post LAM Surveys for Feedback (ongoing) (Bureau/TSU)

LAM2

- CLA Toolkit: Facilitating Participatory & Inclusive Group Process
- Resources: Tools and Techniques for Working in Diverse Groups
- Resources: Working with Unconscious Bias
- Resources for Working Across Cultures

LAM3

- CLA Toolkit: Facilitating Consensus Decision-Making
- Consensus Decision-Making Tip Sheet
- Understanding Cultural Values in Intercultural Groups
- Resources: Tools to Support Working with Conflict

Pre-LAM4

- CLA Resource: Tips for Facilitating Virtual Meetings
- CLA Resource: Resources for Virtual Team Building
- CLA Resource: Template for Leading Groups Online
- Etiquette for Inclusive & Productive Virtual Meetings
- Building Group Agreements within IPCC WGI